

EXA4MIND

D7.2

Dissemination and Communication Interim Report

AUSTRALO

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Abstract

This interim report evaluates the first 18 months of communication and dissemination activities for the EXA4MIND project, assessing progress towards objectives set in Deliverable D7.1 Impact Master Plan (EXA4MIND 2023a). It focuses on stakeholder collaboration and dissemination efforts, detailing achievements, metrics, and outreach evaluations.

Key outcomes include establishing a visual identity and online presence, achieving over 3,500 website visits, 1,150 followers, and 10,000 social media visits. Five communication campaigns generated over 78,000 impressions with a 7% engagement rate. Examples of dissemination efforts are promotional materials, press releases, scientific publications, and posters.

The EXA4MIND strategy, based on an Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework, aims to strengthen communication with stakeholders, ensuring effective and timely information dissemination. Stakeholder engagement involved initiatives like EOSC and BDVA, and led to forming initiatives such as the DataNexus cluster.

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Communication; dissemination; outreach; impact; engagement; stakeholders; social media; impressions; networking; C&D strategies.

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Dissemination Levels

PU Public Public, fully open, e.g. website
SEN Sensitive Confidential to EXA4MIND project and Commission Services

Deliverable Types

R Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)
DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC Websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER Software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DoA	Description of Action
HPC	High Performance Computing
WP	Work Package

Table of Partners

Short name	Partner
IT4I@VSB	IT4Innovations at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava (IT4Innovations) https://www.it4i.cz/en
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities https://www.lrz.de/english/
METU	Middle East Technical University (METU) https://www.metu.edu.tr/
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab https://www.australo.org/
EURAXENT	Euraxent https://www.linkedin.com/company/euraxent/
CVUT	Czech Institute of Informatics, Robotics and Cybernetics at the Czech Technical University (CIIRC CTU) https://www.ciirc.cvut.cz/
VALEO	Valeo https://www.valeo.com/en/czech-republic/
TERRAVIEW	Terraview https://www.terraview.co/
ALTRNATIV	Altrnativ https://altrnativ.com/
VALEO.AI	Valeo.ai https://www.valeo.com/en/valeo-ai/

Executive Summary

The purpose of this deliverable (Communication and Dissemination Interim Report) is to provide **an update on the progress and effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activities** undertaken as part of the project in the first 18 months. It serves as a mid-point evaluation to assess whether communication efforts are on track to achieve the desired outcomes and objectives outlined in the Deliverable D7.1 Impact Master Plan (EXA4MIND 2023a). The scope of the report includes progress update, achievements, metrics and outreach evaluation, and it will serve as a roadmap for continuous successful communication efforts. This report mainly focuses on T7.1. Stakeholder Collaboration Framework, and T7.2. Dissemination and Communication.

The key results presented in this report are the establishment of a visual identity and online presence. The result of this is a website with over 3,500 visits, over 1,150 followers and 10,000 social media accounts visits. We run 5 major communication campaigns and achieved over 78,000 impressions, with an engagement rate of over 7%. In regard to dissemination, we produced promotional materials, press releases and published 6 scientific publications and 4 posters.

As for stakeholder engagement, project members engaged, among others, with initiatives such as **EOSC - European Open Science Cloud**, **BDVA – Big Data Value Association**, **iRODS** and **ETP4HPC – European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing**. The project participated in a sister project workshop and also led the formation of the **DataNexus cluster**, formed by sister projects from call **HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05 - Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions (RIA)**.

The EXA4MIND engagement strategy is built upon an Agile Stakeholder Engagement Framework to continuously develop and strengthen communication streams with key stakeholder groups, reinforcing the impact pathways of the projects through direct and meaningful interactions with its stakeholder base. Additionally, we followed the strategy and tactics for effectively communicating information about the project to relevant stakeholders and the public, ensuring that key messages reach the target audience in a timely and coherent manner.

This deliverable builds on Deliverable D7.1, Impact Master Plan (EXA4MIND 2023a), and is complemented by Deliverable D7.3, Market Analysis and Exploitation Interim Report (EXA4MIND 2024a), providing a comprehensive update on D7.1 (EXA4MIND 2023a). The series will continue with D7.4, Dissemination & Communication Final Report (EXA4MIND 2025a), and D7.5, Market Analysis and Exploitation Final Report (EXA4MIND 2025b), scheduled for completion in month 36. Additionally, next in line are milestone MS22 – A second overview of the cooperation actions with sister projects funded under the same topic and other EU initiatives,

and milestone MS24 – A second overview on publication efforts. Both are due month^o24.

1 Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable (Communication and Dissemination Interim Report) is to provide **an update on the progress and effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activities** undertaken as part of the project in the first 18 months. It serves as a mid-point evaluation to assess whether communication efforts are on track to achieve the desired outcomes and objectives outlined in the D7.1 Impact Master Plan (EXA4MIND 2024a). The scope of the report includes progress update, achievements, metrics and outreach evaluation, and it will serve as a roadmap for continuous successful communication efforts.

The main goal of WP7 is to fast-track and amplify knowledge transfer between EXA4MIND and its target stakeholder base, reinforcing the value streams of the project and capitalising on the results obtained. Part of this goal is achieved through communication and dissemination activity, which is crucial for sharing information, ideas, and knowledge with a target audience in a clear and impactful way.

The Dissemination and Communication Interim Report serves as a valuable tool to assess the effectiveness of EXA4MIND communication efforts and make informed decisions about future communication activities. It helps ensure that communication efforts remain aligned with project goals and objectives, ultimately contributing to the overall success of the project.

Communication facilitates knowledge sharing and learning among project team members, driving innovation and excellence in project execution. This, added to a clear dissemination and communication strategy, can contribute to collaboration and enhanced teamwork. Additionally, effective communication contributes to further engagement of the stakeholders and fosters a commitment to project success. In this report, we will focus on the effectivity of our communication and dissemination efforts, as these play a critical role in the success of EXA4MIND.

As determined in the Impact Master Plan (see Deliverable D7.1, EXA4MIND 2024a), the EXA4MIND engagement strategy is built upon the Agile Marketing Lab Framework© - a methodology designed by the partner AUSTRALO to maximise the performance of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plans, to continuously develop and strengthen communication streams with key stakeholder groups, reinforcing the impact pathways of the projects through direct and meaningful interactions with its stakeholder base. This methodology relies on a constant, carefully designed throughput of promotional activities and campaigns, conceived to incite and maintain the interest of our audience throughout the project's lifecycle.

The previously submitted Impact Master Plan (see Deliverable D7.1, EXA4MIND 2024a) outlined the strategy and tactics for effectively communicating information about the project to relevant stakeholders and the public, ensuring that key messages reach the target audience in a timely and coherent manner. The plan described **two stages**, one spanning between the project’s official kick-off and the submission of this deliverable, and a second phase of heightened maturity between the submission of this document and the end of the project. The first phase (see Figure 1) was designed to focus on identifying relevant stakeholders and crafting a specific value proposition for each stakeholder segment, while the second will be about defining a clear value proposition to further enhance the project’s communication and dissemination (C&D) outreach for example through training and further collaborations.

Figure 1: Timeline for EXA4MIND’s First Operational Stage

While all partners in the consortium are expected to actively contribute to EXA4MIND’s outreach activities in WP7, this work package –and D7.2 specifically– are led by AUSTRALO, who will apply their marketing expertise and proprietary methodologies to help partners unlock the full potential of their research and innovation. Other key actors in WP7 are EURAXENT, in charge of the creation of a long-term sustainability plan for the project, and BADW-LZR, who will lead the efforts on identifying potential contributions to standardisation and exploitation.

This interim report will be followed by a final report, **D7.4 Final Dissemination and communication report** (EXA4MIND 2025a), due month 36 (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Timeline for EXA4MIND’s Second Operational Stage

In regard to the report, **Section 1** serves as an introduction, setting the stage for the subsequent sections.

Section 2 offers a comprehensive reminder of the communication strategy employed by EXA4MIND. It delves into the EXA4MIND C&D tools, elaborating on their functionality and importance. This section also contextualizes the stakeholder engagement efforts, outlining the strategies and methodologies used to foster productive interactions with stakeholders. Furthermore, it highlights the achievements resulting from EXA4MIND's communication efforts, showcasing tangible outcomes and key performance indicators. Additionally, it discusses the engagement with various EU projects and other EU initiatives, emphasizing collaborative efforts and synergies.

Section 3 focuses on the dissemination plan, detailing the systematic approach taken to disseminate information and results. It underscores EXA4MIND's commitment to Open Science, emphasizing the principles of transparency, accessibility, and reproducibility in research. This section also documents the significant achievements in dissemination, providing concrete examples and metrics. Moreover, it includes information about the events attended by members, offering insights into the networking and knowledge-sharing opportunities that these events presented.

Section 4 highlights the outreach achievements, following the showcasing of initiatives and activities aimed at expanding EXA4MIND's reach and impact presented in **Section 3**. It also discusses the formation of the DataNexus cluster, explaining its purpose, structure, and anticipated benefits. This section highlights the importance of collaboration and the role of the cluster in facilitating knowledge sharing and innovation.

Section 5 is dedicated to internal governance and continuous monitoring. It outlines the governance framework, detailing the roles and responsibilities of some members within EXA4MIND. This section also covers the mechanisms in place for continuous monitoring, ensuring that the project remains on track and meets its C&D objectives. It emphasizes the importance of accountability and transparency in project management.

Lastly, **Section 6** presents the conclusion of the report. It synthesizes the key points discussed in the previous sections, providing a cohesive summary and highlighting some key results. This section reflects on the overall progress and achievements of EXA4MIND, and offers insights into future directions and potential areas for further development.

2 Communication Strategy

EXA4MIND **overall objectives for communication** adhere to the following directives:

- ◆ **Plan:** craft and deliver top-level messages about the project to non-technical target groups and audiences.
- ◆ **Reach:** communicate technical and scientific results and benefits to specialised target groups and stakeholders.
- ◆ **Act:** build a solid community/ecosystem.
- ◆ **Convert:** identify leads within the project’s ecosystem and explore their unmet needs and interests to build a solid customer base/ecosystem for future dissemination and exploitation of results.
- ◆ **Engage:** raise awareness among specialised and non-specialised audiences of the added value of EXA4MIND to reach the widest possible community.

By addressing these objectives in a targeted and strategic manner, the communication plan helps ensure that EXA4MIND’s mission, activity and results are effectively communicated and understood, leading to broader engagement and support for the project goals.

2.1 EXA4MIND C&D Tools

The EXA4MIND communication tools are:

- ◆ **EXA4MIND’s visual identity:** including all logo declinations and applications, official fonts and colour palettes.
- ◆ **Online channels:** the project’s official website, social media accounts and newsletter platform of choice (see Figure 3).
- ◆ **Promotional material:** the first batch of promotional materials, including EXA4MIND’s flyer, poster, roll-up banner and merchandise.

Figure 3: Online Channels: Project Website, X, LinkedIn and Brevo

One must identify the most effective communication channels to reach each audience segment. This could include social media, email, websites, blogs, traditional media, events, or direct mail, and develop communication strategies and messages that are tailored to each audience segment. Moreover, one can develop a

plan for disseminating messages to each audience segment through the chosen communication channels. Considering the timing, frequency, and format of your communications is key.

2.1.1 Achievements

In regard to EXA4MIND’s achievements related to **visual identity**, all multimedia materials produced in the context of the project followed EXA4MIND’s visual guidelines and we have achieved a branding recognition that is memorable (see examples of branding in Figure 4). By implementing these strategies, the consortium can foster a culture where all members positively and consistently use the styling and branding, ensuring a cohesive brand presence.

Figure 4: Examples of Branding

The EXA4MIND **public website** already achieved over **3,500 visits** from over **615 unique visitors (47 monthly average)**. The website is a key instrument to boost the visibility of the project and the main entry point to showcase its vision and approach, news, findings and results, introducing visitors to the project’s rationale and educating them on its fundamental concepts.

Figure 5 Updated Website Structure

Website content is reviewed and updated quarterly to reflect project progress, see Figure 5. At present we are discussing how to onboard two new sections on the website: one for the **DataNexus cluster**, and another for the **EXAKI kick-starter initiative**.

The EXA4MIND **helpdesk** and contact point has complied with its commitment for a 72-hours reply to manage general enquiries, collaboration requests, bug-tracking and feature requests.

Contact point | info@exa4mind.eu

With over **1,150 followers** and **10,000 accounts visits** on **social media**, EXA4MIND has established an active presence on both X and LinkedIn (see X and LinkedIn profiles in Figure 6 and Figure 7) and have been highly effective in engaging with technology-driven communities. EXA4MIND’s strategy for social media followed key rules including post regularly, use reference and keyword, actively share content from the community, tailor content to specific audiences and boost promotion of project content.

Figure 6: EXA4MIND X Profile

Figure 7: EXA4MIND LinkedIn Profile

Communication campaigns are a powerful tool for informing, influencing, and engaging audiences, driving both immediate and long-term goals across various fields and industries. In the last 18 months we ran over **5 major communication campaigns** including the ones about general awareness, faces of EXA4MIND, women and girls in science, EXA4MIND events and achievements and EXA4MIND scientific publications. With a total of **484 posts** we achieved over **78,000 impressions**, with an **engagement rate of over 7%**, which demonstrates high engagement from our community. See examples in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 8: ‘Faces of EXA4MIND’ Campaign

Figure 9: Women and Girls in Science Campaign

The EXA4MIND project leverages **social media** for several **key functions**. These include promoting **Open Science** through platforms like Zenodo; sharing members’ **viewpoints**; and **publicising** events. Social media is also used to celebrate **achievements**, highlight important **dates**, communicate relevant **policies**, make publications more **accessible**, share project **developments**, promote **application cases**, and highlight significant **meetings**. Additionally, it supports dissemination through EXA4MIND **newsletters** and shares information about related **initiatives** like sister EU projects. Examples of those can be seen in Figure 10-14.

Figure 10: Publications Showing Member’s Views and Achievements

Figure 11: EXA4MIND at Events

Figure 12 Posts about EXA4MIND Features and Scientific Publications

Figure 13: Posts Promoting EU Policies and Key Events

Figure 14: News and Highlights

The EXA4MIND **YouTube** channel (see Figure 15), established in February 2024, already received over 125 views. Through YouTube we are able to share and engage with a wide range of interested users through EXA4MIND related video content. Within the EXA4MIND context, YouTube's importance lies in its role in building communities.

Figure 15: EXA4MIND YouTube Profile

YouTube | https://www.youtube.com/@EXA4MIND_EU

We also **combine** the use of our own **social media** channels to amplify the outreach and effectiveness of our communication and dissemination (see example in Figure 16).

Figure 16: Promotion of YouTube Channel on LinkedIn

The project produced **4 newsletters** in this first period, engaging **225 subscribers** (175 on LinkedIn and 50 in Brevo). The newsletters were published on both LinkedIn and Brevo, reaching both a professional and general audience, hence expanding our network, see examples in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Examples of EXA4MIND Newsletters

Additionally, EXA4MIND was **mentioned 45+ times** in member’s publications, and it was specifically **featured** in the IT4I@VSB¹ and AUSTRALO² newsletters and the HiPEAC Magazine³ (issue 71) as can be seen in Figure 18 Figure 18: AUSTRALO May 2024 Newsletter and Figure 19.

Figure 18: AUSTRALO May 2024 Newsletter and IT4I@VSB Newsletter (May 2024)

Figure 19: EXA4MIND Featured in HiPEAC (Issue 71) (January 2024)

¹ IT4I@VSB May 2024 newsletter: <https://mailchi.mp/it4i/it4innovations-newsletter-10311007>

² AUSTRALO May 2024 newsletter: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/latest-australo-newsletter-out-australoteam-jysrf/?trackingId=byV3x6p2RJ2UQGZUhW6TgO%3D%3D>

³ HiPEAC Magazine: <https://www.hipeac.net/magazine/7167.pdf>

Disseminating material on social media is crucial for expanding reach, fostering community, raising awareness, enhancing credibility, and encouraging engagement. EXA4MIND was also **featured** in partner’s social media channels therefore increasing its reach. Based on our records, our partners contributed with over **17K+ impressions** related to EXA4MIND publications, see Figure 20.

Figure 20: Member’s Publication of EXA4MIND Posts

In terms of **promotion** EXA4MIND produced **3 press releases**⁴ (see Figure 21), and a number of slide decks and infographics. Press releases are a strategic tool that helps organisations communicate effectively, manage their public image, and engage with various stakeholders. The **slide deck** and **infographics** are powerful engagement tools to share the project’s vision and scope with specialised audiences in a clear, straightforward and visually attractive way (see example in Figure 22). We will enhance and expand this dissemination material to develop customized tools in the second half of the project.

⁴ Launch press release: <https://zenodo.org/records/7530389>

StandICT collaboration press release: <https://zenodo.org/records/12653891>

DataNexus cluster press release: <https://zenodo.org/records/12654145>

Figure 21: EXA4MIND Press Releases

Figure 22 Example of EXA4MIND Presentation Slides

The produced **promotional materials**⁵ for EXA4MIND are the project’s official **flyer**, a number of **posters**, **booth presentations**, a **roll-up banner** design and **stickers**, together with branded **merchandise items** (i.e. tote bags, charging cables, NFC stickers, coasters) that promote EXA4MIND in a creative and sustainable way, see examples in Figure 23. Promotional materials play a vital role in C&D strategies by increasing visibility, engaging stakeholders, conveying information, and nurturing loyalty.

⁵ EXA4MIND roll up: <https://zenodo.org/records/11681611>
 EXA4MIND poster: <https://zenodo.org/records/11680789>
 EXA4MIND leaflet: <https://zenodo.org/records/7923757>

Figure 23: Examples of Promotional Materials

We also produced **branded computer backgrounds** that members can use at project meetings, reviews and meetings with other stakeholders, see example in Figure 24. Branded computer backgrounds can serve as a simple yet powerful tool for reinforcing brand identity, maintaining professionalism, and leveraging every digital interaction as a C&D opportunity.

Figure 24: Example of Computer Background

Contact points are interactions or points of contact between a person and a brand, in this case, EXA4MIND. If we are to consider that we had 615 website unique visitors; we have 1150 followers; 25+ students attended the EUDAT summer school and our members attended over 20 events (with an average engagement of 30 people per event), and engaged with over 20 initiatives, we can estimate that we had over 3,000 contact points in the first half of the project.

The resulting communication KPIs are presented in Table 1:

Focus	KPIs	Achieved	Target
Community	Contact points	3,000+	5,000
	EU associations and create synergies with EDIHs	10+	10+
Online channels	Unique average monthly website visitors	47	300
	Social media monthly impressions	4,300	4,500
	Social media followers	1,159	2,500
	Newsletter	4	quarterly
Promotional materials	Features in external newsletters	3	4
	Hard copy items	1,000+	1,000
	Graphic elements (e.g. infographics, banners)	50+	100+
	Videos (teasers and interviews)	3+	3

Table 1: Status of Communication KPIs

2.2 Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is essential for building strong relationships, gaining support, managing risks, fostering innovation, and ensuring the long-term success of the project. As part of the communication plan, the **stakeholder engagement** related activity included the establishment of a high-level baseline of relevant profiles/expertise for the project to liaise with, and the identification of links between key actors within the project’s ecosystem.

The identified engagement **key target groups** are: technology and data providers, the industrial ecosystem, partnerships and networks, policy makers, social innovators and society as a whole. Key groups and selected C&D tools and strategies are listed in Table 2.

	Technology & Data Providers	Industrial Ecosystem	Partnerships and Networks	Policy Makers	Social Innovators	Society as a Whole
Website	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social Media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press Releases	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Slide Decks & one Pagers	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Multimedia	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mailing Campaigns	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Project Docs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Peer-reviewed Publications	✓	✓		✓		
Technical Publications	✓	✓		✓		
Open Access Repository	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Stakeholder Consultation	✓	✓		✓		
Conferences & Workshops	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Congresses, Exhibitions & Demo Spaces	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 2: EXA4MIND C&D Tools and Target Audiences

It is important to effectively **select target audiences and right C&D tools and strategies** for communication and dissemination so that we ensure that messages are reaching the right people in the most effective way possible. Selecting a target audience and C&D tools and strategies allows you to focus your efforts, resources, and messaging to maximise your communication effectiveness and achieve better results. Additionally, when you know who your target audience is, you can create messaging and content that resonates with them on a deeper level. This increases

the chances of making a connection and building relationships and potential collaborations.

2.2.1 Achievements

EXA4MIND benefited from the very **active participation** of its partners in very diverse working groups and initiatives around HPC, Extreme Data mining and analytics, and more specifically within data science & Big Data, computer science, Open Science & Research, HPC, Agriculture (data related), 6G, AI and automotive.

For example, in the segment of data science and Big Data, members engaged with initiatives such as **EUDAT – Collaborative Data Infrastructure**⁶, **EOSC - European Open Science Cloud**⁷, **BDVA – Big Data Value Association**⁸ and **iRODS**⁹ through membership, service use, consultation, validation, task forces and working groups. Similarly, in regards to HPC, members engaged with **ETP4HPC – European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing**¹⁰, **EuroHPC JU**¹¹, **EuroCC**¹² and **the GCS – Gauss Centre for Supercomputing**¹³. Additionally, members engaged with AI related initiatives including the **prg.ai Association**¹⁴, the **ELLIS - European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems**¹⁵ and **CVS - the Computer vision foundation**¹⁶.

For the next stage of the project, we will aim to consolidate these relationships to capitalise on those for the benefit of the project.

Details of engagement are presented in Table 3.

Segment	Initiative	Partner	Type of Engagement
Data science & Big Data	The Alliance for Digital Trust	ALTRNATIV	Active contact.
Data science & Big Data	ACM - Association for Computing Machinery	METU	Active contact.
Data science & Big Data	EUDAT – Collaborative Data Infrastructure	IT4I@VSB	Active participation and full membership in EUDAT and service ownership of B2SAFE.
Data science & Big Data	EOSC - European Open Science Cloud	IT4I@VSB	Active participation and full membership.

⁶ EUDAT: <https://www.eudat.eu> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

⁷ Open Science Cloud: <https://eosc-portal.eu> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

⁸ BDVA: <https://bdva.eu> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

⁹ IRODS: <https://irods.org/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹⁰ ETP4HPC: <https://www.etp4hpc.eu/membership.html> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹¹ EuroHPC JU: https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹² EuroCC: <https://www.eurocc-access.eu> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹³ Gauss Centre: <https://www.gauss-centre.eu> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹⁴ Prg.ai: <https://prg.ai> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹⁵ ELLIS: <https://ellis.eu> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹⁶ CVF: <https://www.thecvf.com> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

Data science & Big Data	<u>BDVA – Big Data Value Association</u>	IT4I@VSB, AUSTRALO	Active participation and full membership.
Data science & Big Data	<u>NFDI – The German National Research Data Infrastructure</u>	BADW-LRZ	Active contact.
Data science & Big Data	<u>iRODS</u>	IT4I@VSB	Active contact and full membership.
Computer science	<u>IEEE – Computer Society</u>	METU, IT4I@VSB	Active contact.
Open Science & Research	<u>RDA (Research Data Alliance) and interest group RDARI</u>	BADW-LRZ	Active contact.
Open Science & Research	<u>RDA-DE</u>	BADW-LRZ	Active contact.
Open Science & Research	<u>EOSC CZ</u>	IT4I@VSB	Active contact.
HPC	<u>ETP4HPC – European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing</u>	IT4I@VSB	Active participation.
HPC	<u>EuroHPC JU</u>	IT4I@VSB	Active contact.
HPC	<u>EuroCC</u>	IT4I@VSB, BADW-LRZ, METU	Active participation.
HPC	<u>GCS – Gauss Centre for Supercomputing</u>	BADW-LRZ	Active contact.
Agriculture	<u>Swiss Food and Nutrition Valley Association</u>	TERRAVIEW	Active participation and membership.
Agriculture	<u>Agropole</u>	TERRAVIEW	Active contact.
6G	<u>6GSNS JU Associate membership</u>	TERRAVIEW	Active contact and associate membership.
AI	<u>prg.ai Association</u>	VALEO, CVUT	Active participation and membership.
AICzechia	<u>https://www.aiczechia.cz/</u>	CIIRC CTU, IT4I	Active participation.
Automotive	<u>Automotive Industry Association</u>	VALEO	Active contact and membership.
AI	<u>European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems (ELLIS)</u>	CIIRC CVUT	Active participation and membership.
AI	<u>Computer vision foundation (CVF)</u>	CIIRC CVUT	Active contact.

Table 3: EXA4MIND Stakeholder Engagement

Engaging with these organisations is crucial for advancing research and innovation across multiple sectors, including computing and digital technologies, data infrastructure, big data analytics, high-performance computing (HPC), AI and machine learning, digital trust and security, and sector-specific applications like

agriculture and automotive technologies. These organisations provide valuable resources, collaboration opportunities, and access to cutting-edge knowledge, technology and standards, which are essential for driving progress, fostering collaboration, and maintaining competitiveness in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

2.3 Other EU Projects and Initiatives

Engaging with other **European projects and initiatives** is highly relevant as it facilitates access to a wealth of resources and collaborative networks, fostering further research, innovation and growth.

2.3.1 Other EU Projects

For example, EXA4MIND members attended the Get-to-know introductory workshop and welcome day to HE Data projects (WP2021-22)¹⁷ on February 2023. This meeting brought together representatives from 26 new projects in Horizon Europe Cluster 4 – Destination 3, as well as colleagues from **BDVA** and the new **Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC)**¹⁸.

Additionally, in April 2023, EXA4MIND successfully led the formation of the **DataNexus Cluster**, the group formed by seven sister projects from the **HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05 - Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions (RIA)**¹⁹ call. The seven projects participating in this cluster are: **EXTRACT**²⁰, **EFRA**²¹, **GraphMassivizer**²², **NEARDATA**²³, **SYCLOPS**²⁴, **EMERALDS**²⁵ and **EXA4MIND**. The cluster is presented in detail in Section 4.2

2.3.2 Other EU Initiatives – EDIH

Jan Martinovič presented EXA4MIND and his Advanced Data Analysis and Simulations Lab and services to various industrial partners, SMEs and public organisations at the official presentation of the activities of the **European Digital Innovation Hub (EDIH) Ostrava in the Czech Republic**²⁶. The EDIH Ostrava provides

¹⁷ Introductory workshop and welcome day to HE Data projects - <https://bdva.eu/events/get-to-know-introductory-workshop-and-welcome-day-to-he-data-projects-wp2021-22/>

¹⁸ DSSC - <https://dssc.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

¹⁹ **HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05** (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²⁰ EXTRACT - <https://extract-project.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²¹ EFRA - <https://efraproject.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²² Graph-Massivizer - <https://graph-massivizer.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²³ NEARDATA - <https://neardata.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²⁴ SYCLOPS - <https://www.syclops.org/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²⁵ EMERALDS - <https://emeralds-horizon.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

²⁶ EDIH Ostrava - <https://edihostrava.cz/en/> (Accessed on 14/06/24)

clients with a complete portfolio of services which focus primarily on supporting SMEs and start-ups as well as public organisations in deploying and using digital technologies.

3 Dissemination Plan

EXA4MIND has developed a flexible dissemination plan that intends to raise awareness of project results, promoting understanding and encouraging action among key target audiences. The execution of this plan will facilitate the uptake of outcomes and best practices, as well as promote research insights and breakthroughs, thus reinforcing the impacts described in the DoA.

The EXA4MIND dissemination methodology also takes place in two stages. Between month 1 and month 18 we have focused on analysing the project's stakeholder framework and engaging and collaborating with identified target groups. From month 19 we will continue to engage with our stakeholders with the ambition to build a strong community of practice, and we will focus on showcasing EXA4MIND's tangible achievements by for example participating and/or hosting workshops, ad hoc events and tutorials/webinars.

As the project reaches its final stretch, we expect to attract more attention from stakeholders interested in near-final results. Further participation in events, workshops, conferences, together with partner contribution to publications will be key to broadcast the project's final insights and foster long-term sustainability of its results.

3.1 Open Science

EXA4MIND is a solid advocate of **Open Science**, a policy priority for the European Commission and the standard provision under which its research and innovation funding programmes operate. Open science aims to make scientific research, data, and dissemination accessible to everyone, promoting transparency, collaboration, and innovation. By making research findings openly available, the European Commission seeks to maximize the impact of research and innovation for the benefit of society as a whole.

Making research openly available increases its potential impact by allowing a broader audience, including other researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and the public, to benefit from it, while it also promotes public engagement with research and enhances public trust in science by making research more accessible and understandable to everyone. Moreover, open science facilitates the sharing of research findings and data relevant to addressing societal challenges, such as climate change, public health, and sustainable development.

Lastly, open science ensures that research findings, data, and methodologies are openly available, making it easier for other researchers to verify and reproduce results. By sharing research findings openly, scientists can build on each other's work more effectively, leading to faster progress and innovation. Open science encourages collaboration among researchers, institutions, and countries, fostering a more collaborative and interconnected research community.

3.2 Achievements

EXA4MIND's dissemination areas, KPIs and targets are presented below in Table 4.

Area	KPIs	Achieved	Target
Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific items in journals	1P+1A+2R*	10
	Peer-reviewed papers in conferences/workshops (including peer-reviewed posters)	5P+1A+4R* /2 posters	15
	Awareness publications (including press releases)	35	50+
	Open Access downloads (Zenodo)	530	1,000+
Events	Attended events	23	30
	Webinars and workshops	3	12
	Unique participants	25+	300

*P-published; A-accepted; R-under review.

Table 4: Status of Dissemination KPIs

Figure 25: Dissemination Platforms

As part of EXA4MIND's commitment to Open Science we have a dedicated EXA4MIND **ZENODO community** and repository in place (see Figure 26). In the first phase of the project EXA4MIND ZENODO repository had **466 views** and **561 downloads**. Additionally, published Open Access scientific publications gathered **1,285 views**.

Figure 26: EXA4MIND ZENODO Community

ZENODO

<https://zenodo.org/communities/exa4mind-heurope>

Project documentation in the form of **public deliverables** and all produced **scientific publications** are available through the **project website** in the **Publications section**²⁷. These are also promoted via articles (**News section**)²⁸ and social media publications (see Figure 27). Publishing public deliverables and scientific publications is essential for promoting transparency, accountability, knowledge sharing, collaboration, public engagement, and compliance with regulations and funding requirements. It serves as a cornerstone of open and responsible research and project management practices.

²⁷ EXA4MIND publications website section: <https://exa4mind.eu/publications/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

²⁸ EXA4MIND News website section: <https://exa4mind.eu/news/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

Figure 27: Examples of Publication Dissemination on Social Media

With its Open Science approach supporting reproducibility, EXA4MIND is preparing for publishing significant portions of data as well as codes pertaining to the platform or application cases. For code development, source-code management and open-source publication, we use the “Opencode” GitLab instance hosted at IT4I@VSB as shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: EXA4MIND GitLab

GitLab

<https://opencode.it4i.eu/exa4mind>

For the next stage of the project, we aim to focus on tailoring key messages to key audiences, online surveys and consultations via GDPR-compliant survey management platforms (like the European Commission’s very own **EU Survey**), so that we establish bi-directional **feedback** and information flows that promotes the project and potential collaboration opportunities (e.g. matchmaking, publishing, joint events).

3.3 Open Access Peer-Reviewed Publications and Posters, and Awareness Articles

EXA4MIND members published in top refereed **scientific journals and conferences**, capitalising on the experience from research partners. Scientific publications are the cornerstone of the research enterprise, playing a fundamental role in advancing knowledge, fostering collaboration, and driving scientific progress.

The consortium published in **journals and conferences** such as: IEEE Big Data, Intelligent Data Mining, the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, the International Journal of Computer Vision (IJCV), the Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation (JCTC), the IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), the conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), Transactions on Machine Learning Research (TMLR), and ISGC&HEPiX2023. Publishing here signifies contributing to highly respected and impactful platforms within the fields of data science, computer vision, automation, machine learning, and computational science. These initiatives are recognised for their rigorous peer-review processes and are frequented by leading researchers, making them ideal for disseminating cutting-edge research, gaining visibility in the scientific community, and advancing academic and professional careers.

Table 5 presents the **scientific publications** published or accepted, including their statuses and titles.

Type of Publication	Status	Title
Journal Paper	Published	Mlýnský V., Kührová P., Stadlbauer P., Krepl M., Otyepka M., Banáš P., and Šponer J. (2023). “Simple Adjustment of Intranucleotide Base-Phosphate Interaction in the OL3 AMBER Force Field Improves RNA Simulations” . (JCTC) Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation , Volume 9, Issue 22, Pages 8423-8433.
Scientific Conference Paper	Published	Harsh P., Hachinger S., Derquennes M., Edmonds A., Karagoz P., Golawski G., Hayek M. and Martinovič J. (2023). “Wine in the Cloud, or: Smart Vineyards with a Distributed “Extreme Data Database” and Supercomputing” . ISGC&HEPiX2023. Proceedings of Science, Volume 434.
Scientific Conference Paper	Published	Vobecký A., Siméoni O., Hurych D., Gidaris S., Bursuc A., Perez A., Sivic J. (2024) “POP-3D: Open-Vocabulary 3D Occupancy Prediction from Images” (pre-print version) . (NeurIPS) Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2023 .

Scientific Conference Paper	Published	Mahdi Khosravi M., Karagoz P., Hakki Toroslu I. (2024) <u>“IndexAI: AI Based Index Selection for NoSQL Databases” (pre-print version). IEEE Big Data 2023, 9th Special Session on Intelligent Data Mining.</u> Proc. of 2023 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (BigData), pp. 5818-5825.
Scientific Conference Paper	Published	Cekinel F., Karagoz P., Coltekin C. (2024) <u>“Cross-Lingual Learning vs. Low-Resource Fine-Tuning: A Case Study with Fact-Checking in Turkish”.</u> LRA and ICCL.
Scientific Conference Paper	Published	Puy G., Gidaris S., Boulch A., Siméoni O., Sautier C., Pérez P., Bursuc A., Marlet R. (2024) <u>“Three Pillars improving Vision Foundation Model Distillation for Lidar” (pre-print version).</u> CVPR. Proc. of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), pp. 21519-21529
Journal Paper	Accepted	MOCA: Self-supervised Representation Learning by Predicting Masked Online Codebook Assignments
Scientific Conference Paper	Accepted	Towards Motion Forecasting with Real-World Perception Inputs: Are End-to-End Approaches Competitive?

Table 5: Table Listing EXA4MIND Scientific Publications

In total, and as per month 18, members published **1 journal paper** and **5 scientific conference papers** (out of which 1 is not Open Access but the pre-print is on ZENODO, and 2 are pre-print versions. We are waiting for final published versions). **2 further scientific conference papers** are accepted, and **4** more are **under review**. Additionally, **1 journal paper** is accepted, and **2 journal papers** are under review.

The consortium also produced **4 posters**^{29,30,31} - playing a crucial role in knowledge dissemination, collaboration, and academic growth within the research community - presented at events such as **NeurIPS2023**³², the **High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering (HPCSE 2024)**³³ and the **IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition 2024 (CVPR)**³⁴. Figure 29 presents examples from the two peer-reviewed posters presented at NeurIPS2023 and CVPR 2024.

²⁹ POP3D: Open-Vocabulary 3D Occupancy Prediction from Images - <https://zenodo.org/records/12704479> (Accessed on 10/07/2024)

³⁰ ADAMS4SIMS – Database Curation for MD Simulations - <https://zenodo.org/records/12704253> (Accessed on 10/07/2024)

³¹ OccFeat: Self-supervised Occupancy Feature Prediction for Pretraining BEV Segmentation Networks - <https://zenodo.org/records/12704307> (Accessed on 10/07/2024)

³² NeurIPS2023 - <https://neurips.cc/Conferences/2023> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

³³ HPCSW2024 - <https://hpcse.it4i.cz/HPCSE24/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

³⁴ CVPR 2024 - <https://cvpr.thecvf.com/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

These events bring together international specialists in high performance computing, applied mathematics, numerical analysis, high performance data analytics, machine/deep learning, quantum computing, and advanced visualization, to exchange experience and ideas, and initiate new research collaborations. Some of the consortium members also participated in round tables.

Figure 29: Poster Presentations at NeurIPS 2023 and CVPR2024

Lastly, the project website presents **35+ awareness publications** that help maximise the project’s online visibility and reach, see examples in Figure 30: Examples of News on the Website. Awareness publications are essential tools for promoting an informed, engaged, and equitable society. They serve as vehicles for knowledge dissemination, advocacy, and empowerment, contributing to positive social change.

The awareness articles are presented within the News section in the project website and have the intention to provide the general public and other stakeholders information, updates, facts, and pointers to resources that help increase understanding and awareness of the challenges the project is aiming to address.

Discover Exa4Mind, with its latest news, stories, activities and upcoming events.

<p><u>EXA4MIND hosts its third plenary meeting in Garching, Munich</u></p> <p>Read More</p>		
<p><u>EXA4MIND at the Data Week 2023</u></p> <p>Read More</p>		

Figure 30: Examples of News on the Website

3.4 Events

Events (e.g. Conferences, congresses, seminars, trade fairs, exhibitions) are a strategic mechanism to put EXA4MIND’s results under the spotlight, while actively interacting and engaging with multiple stakeholders.

Events provide an opportunity to network with other professionals, researchers, and practitioners in the field. These connections can lead to collaborations, partnerships, and the exchange of ideas. Attending events facilitates knowledge sharing and learning about the latest research, trends, and best practices in the field. You can gain insights from keynote speakers, presentations, and workshops.

Presenting at or attending events can also increase visibility within a specific field. It allows to showcase work, share expertise, and build reputation as a reference leader. Events also provide a platform to receive feedback from peers and experts in the field. This can help refine ideas, improve research, and identify new opportunities for collaboration.

Lastly, events are an effective way to disseminate research findings to a wider audience. Whether presenting a paper, giving a poster presentation or participating in a panel discussion, events provide a platform to share research with others in the field.

Table 6 presents the list of **events** that the consortium has already attended on behalf of EXA4MIND as part of the projects networking and outreach strategy. It also lists the upcoming events in which the partners are planning to participate and share EXA4MIND’s insights and progress.

Event	Start Date	Location	Status	Update
<u>ISGC – International Symposium of Grids and Clouds 2023 (With the Environmental Computing Workshop)</u>	19/03/23	Taipei, TW	Delivered	Presented
<u>EuroHPC Summit 2023</u>	20/03/23	Gothenburg, SE	Delivered	Presented
<u>ITS European Congress</u>	22/05/23	Lisbon, PT	Delivered	Presented
<u>ISC High Performance 2023</u>	21/05/2023	Hamburg, DE	Delivered	Presented
<u>Data Week 23</u>	13/06/23	Lulea, SE	Delivered	Panellist
<u>CVPR – The IEEE / CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference</u>	18/06/23	Vancouver, CA	Delivered	Presented
<u>EUDAT Summer School</u>	26/06/23	Kajaani, Finland	Delivered	Presented
<u>Ostrava EDIH Day</u>	10/05/23	Ostrava, CR	Delivered	Attended
<u>EuChems ComChem 2023</u>	27/08/23	Thessaloniki, GR	Delivered	Presented
<u>ICCV – International Conference on Computer Vision</u>	02/10/23	Paris, FR	Delivered	Presented
<u>EBDVF – European Big Data Value Forum</u>	25/10/23	Valencia, ES	Delivered	Project booth
<u>SC23</u>	12/11/23	Denver, CO	Delivered	Project booth
<u>Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2023)</u>	10/12/23	New Orleans, USA	Delivered	Presented

<u>IEEE International Conference on Big Data</u>	15/12/23	Sorrento, IT	Delivered	Presented
<u>Euro CC2 Turkey</u>	22/12/23	Online	Delivered	Workshop and demo
<u>HiPEAC2024</u>	17/01/24	Munich, GER	Delivered	Presented
<u>ISGC – International Symposium on Grids and Clouds 2024 (With the Environmental Computing Workshop)</u>	24/03/24	Taipei, TW	Delivered	Presented
<u>e-infra CZ conference</u>	29/04/24	Prague, CZ	Delivered	Presented
<u>ISC High Performance 2024</u>	12/05/24	Hamburg, DE	Delivered	Project booth
<u>HPCSE - High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering 2024</u>	20/05/24	Ostrava, CZ	Delivered	Presented
<u>ICRA IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation</u>	13/05/24	Yokohama, Japan	Delivered	Presented
<u>LREC-COLING</u>	20/05/24	Torino, IT	Delivered	Presented
<u>iRODS UGM 2024</u>	28/05/24	Amsterdam NL	Delivered	Presented
<u>CVPR – The IEEE / CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference</u>	17/06/24	Seattle, USA	Delivered	Presented
<u>European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)</u>	2/10/24	Budapest, HU	Upcoming	Booth/Special session with sister projects
<u>EOSC Symposium 2024</u> https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-symposium-2024/	21/10/24	Berlin, GER	Upcoming	Present
<u>Supercomputing 2024 (SC24)</u>	17/11/24	Atlanta,GA, USA	Upcoming	Project booth
<u>Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS 2024)</u>	09/12/24	Vancouver, CA	Upcoming	Presentati on

Table 6: List of Events that Members Attended and Future Events

3.4.1 Information Booths at Events

EXA4MIND was present at five major events and venues like ITS European Congress³⁵, the ISC High Performance³⁶, the European Big Data Value Forum

³⁵ ITS European Congress - <https://itseuropeancongress.com/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

³⁶ ICS High Performance - <https://www.isc-hpc.com/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

(EBDVF)³⁷, and the International Conference for High-Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis (SC)³⁸ with presentation booths, an effective way to engage with attendees, share information, demonstrate the project's offerings, increase brand visibility and generate leads during the event.

At the booth, members engaged with attendees and encouraged them to engage with the research. The booths also provided an opportunity to share information about the members, increasing organisations' visibility, and to highlight key features, benefits and findings of the project. A booth is also an opportunity to generate leads by capturing the contact information of interested attendees and follow up with them after the event.

One of the strategies followed by the team to further promote engagement with the project's content via social media and the newsletter, was to organise a draw, which awarded three lucky winners with external hard disks as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: EXA4MIND Raffle at ISC 2023 Event

Booths at events provide very valuable opportunities to engage with different stakeholders, see Figure 32. For example, at **ISC High Performance 2023**, IT4Inovations introduced the EXA4MIND project at the **booth** of the Czech National

³⁷ EBDVF - <https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

³⁸ SC - <https://supercomputing.org/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

Supercomputing Centre. IT4I@VSB screened slides that presented the main information about the EXA4MIND project, distributed branded leaflets and stickers and prepared a prize draw for the attendees of the conference. There was also a booth at **ISC High Performance 2024**.

EXA4MIND also had a **booth** at the **European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2023**, an event that brought together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers from all over Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions, and industrial and research activities in the areas of Data and AI.

Moreover, the IT4I@VSB had a **booth** at the SC2023 International Conference for High-Performance Computing, Networking, Storage, and Analysis. Among other projects, the team also promoted EXA4MIND.

Figure 32: Examples of EXA4MIND Presence in Booths

Lastly in this section, EXA4MIND members have presented and published at two of the **world's most renown conferences** in Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence: the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision and the Neural Information Processing Symposium³⁹.

³⁹ Conference rankings – <https://research.com/conference-rankings/computer-science/computer-vision> and <https://research.com/conference-rankings/computer-science/machine-learning> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

3.4.2 Workshops, Educational Activities and Demonstrations

EUDAT Summer School 2023⁴⁰ took place from 26 to 30 June 2023 in Kajaani, Finland. It was organised in collaboration with the DICE project, aimed to strengthen the skills required to excel in data management, getting the participants geared up to manage and process data throughout the full, research-data lifecycle. Members from IT4I@VSB joined the summer school mentioning EXA4MIND project as trainers and guided students combining traditional theoretical lessons with hands-on sessions (see Figure 33 and Figure 34).

Figure 33: EXA4MIND at EUDAT 2023 Summer School I

⁴⁰ EUDAT Summer School 2023 - <https://eudat.eu/summer-schools/eudat-summer-school-2023> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

Figure 34: EXA4MIND at EUDAT 2023 Summer School II

Additionally, members from METU led the ‘From Natural Language to Database Querying: Large Language Models and Current Trends’ **workshop**. This workshop was part of the EuroCC 2 Turkey seminars (see Figure 34), which aimed to introduce national/public IT workers to SotA concepts in various topics. Members gave a lecture and did a demonstration session.

Figure 35: Program for the EuroCC 2 & EXA4MIND Online Event

Another activity also led by the METU team was the moderation of a working group session in the national HPC conference **BASARIM 2024**⁴¹. At this session the team also shared their experience with Large Language Models (LLM) in the EXA4MIND project. The event took place at the METU campus in Ankara, between 15-17 May 2024.

Members from IT4I@VSB together with the **EUMaster4HPC**⁴² programme students welcomed the visitors of the summit to the **EuroHPC Demo Lab**⁴³ during the **EuroHPC Summit 2023**⁴⁴. They offered attendees **live showcases** of the Karolina supercomputer and presented the LEXIS Platform, which plays a crucial role in the EXA4MIND project. The EuroHPC Summit is one of the most important conferences in Europe and in 2023 the theme was ‘European Supercomputing Excellence in the Exascale Era’. The event was organised by the EuroHPC JU and gathered more than 500 experts from the European HPC community, including providers, scientific and industrial users, and policymakers.

Figure 36: Publication about EXAMIND Presence at SC 2023

Also in 2023, the **Data Week**⁴⁵, which is the spring gathering of the Big Data and Data Driven AI research and innovation community in Europe took place in Lulea, Sweden, from 13 to 15 June 2023 with the central theme ‘Data Meets Infrastructure at the Edge’. Jan Martinovič was one of the **speakers** of the session ‘Are current

⁴¹ BASARIM 2024: <https://indico.truba.gov.tr/event/140/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

⁴² EUMaster4HPC: - https://eumaster4hpc.eu/?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAjw1K-zBhBIEiwAWeCOFyyG84w2HNK2ULJp0lwCOwLBF2O7Jqf9zjSk_uDSEGgaKkHzyrna6BoCFM4QAvD_BwE (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

⁴³ EuroHPC Demo Lab: <https://www.eurohpcsummit.eu/demo-lab> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

⁴⁴ EuroHPC Summit 2023: https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/news-events-0/events/eurohpc-summit-2023-2023-03-20_en (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

⁴⁵ Data Week 2023 -<https://bdva.eu/events/data-week-2023/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

infrastructures suitable for extreme data processing? Technologies for data management’. The speakers in the session focused on Data Management Technologies, analysed the suitability of the current infrastructure for extreme data and provided the latest insights in this area.

IT4I@VSB also participated in the **HiPEAC 2024**⁴⁶ conference (see Figure 37), which gathered experts in computer architecture, programming models, compilers, and operating systems applicable to general purpose, embedded, and cyber-physical systems. The conference featured 74 sessions, including a **workshop** on projects cross-synergy in advancing exascale platforms and quantum computing (**CONCERTO**). The workshop, in which the EXA4MIND team participated (see Figure 37), was designed to promote discussions between academic researchers and industrial companies engaged in various European projects. It aimed to emphasize the unique characteristics of these projects and foster collaborative efforts, which are essential for developing next-generation exascale platforms. Looking ahead to the new European petascale, pre-exascale systems, and the forthcoming exascale supercomputers, the workshop offered a unique platform to share ideas and outcomes. This included discussions on incorporating cutting-edge heterogeneous hardware solutions like quantum computing and neuromorphic devices, specific software components and frameworks, and adapting large and complex application workflows for these advanced systems.

Figure 37: EXA4MIND Project at HiPEAC 2024

⁴⁶ HiPEAC 2024 - <https://www.hipeac.net/2024/munich/#/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

Lastly, Martin Golasowski from the IT4I@VSB, presented the objectives of the EXA4MIND project and a planned extension of the data staging capabilities of the LEXIS Platform in his talk at the **e-INFRA CZ conference 2024**⁴⁷ (see Figure 38). He also provided a live **demonstration** of a containerised AI workflow orchestrated by LEXIS running on IT4I@VSB supercomputers. This event held in Prague, brought together an assembly of researchers, academics, and experts interested in enhancing the Czech Republic’s research infrastructure. This annual event, known for spotlighting the latest trends and innovations in the environment providing complex capacities and resources for the transmission, storage and processing of scientific data to all entities engaged in research and development, continues to serve as a pivotal platform for discussing advancements and fostering collaborations across various scientific disciplines.

Figure 38: EXA4MIND Presence at e-INFRA Event

Attending, participating and presenting at these prominent events such as ISGC, EuroHPC Summit, ISC High Performance, CVPR, ICCV, and NeurIPS, offered significant exposure of the EXA4MIND cutting-edge developments in high-performance computing, computer vision, big data, and information processing. These conferences and symposiums provided a platform for researchers and professionals to showcase their latest findings, network with industry leaders, and stay updated on technological advancements. Participation in these events will potentially lead to collaborative opportunities and increased visibility in the

⁴⁷ E-INFRA CZ Conference - <https://www.e-infra.cz/en/e-infra-cz-conference> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

scientific, technological and industrial communities, thus fostering innovation and contributing to the advancement of various fields.

4 Outreach – Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination outreach involves assessing the effectiveness, reach, and impact of communication activities. Beyond C&D plans' clear objectives, outcomes and key performance indicators, we also collect relevant data throughout our communication campaigns to be able to further assess the outreach and effectiveness of our C&D efforts. Data sources include website analytics, Google Analytics and social media insights. We analyse the data quarterly and continuously improve our communication and dissemination strategies based on the insights gained.

4.1 Achievements

Establishing metrics is a way to measure the effectiveness of communication efforts, such as reach, engagement, click-through rates, and feedback. Those have been presented above but in summary EXA4MIND achieved over **3,000 contact points and 70K+ impressions** in the first 18 months of the project. This data shows that we are reaching and resonating with our audience.

The outreach of EXA4MIND dissemination goes beyond Europe and, as demonstrated by the data, its community is establishing in places such as the USA, see Figure 39. This globalisation of its community suggests that its mission and resources are resonating with people worldwide. It also highlights the universal importance of Big and Extreme Data, regardless of geographical location.

Figure 39: EXA4MIND Community Geolocation – May 2024

EXA4MIND has a well-defined target audience for dissemination efforts. Focusing on technology and data providers, the industrial ecosystem, partnerships and networks, policy makers, social innovators, and society at large is a comprehensive approach.

With over 50% of engagement coming from research services, IT services, IT consulting and software development, it seems like EXA4MIND is effectively reaching professionals in engineering and information technology fields, see Figure 40. This data could inform future strategies for content creation and outreach efforts to continue engaging these key groups effectively.

Figure 40: Data About Sectors that Engagement Comes from

Building a community of over **1,150 followers** within 18 months with a **7% engagement rate** demonstrates the value and interest in the consortium's work. Participating in over **20 events** in various countries also indicates a proactive approach to networking and knowledge sharing. Engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders, from researchers and businesses to policymakers and social innovators, shows a holistic approach to collaboration and impact. EXA4MIND is making significant strides in advancing its goals and fostering connections within the relevant ecosystems.

In summary, EXA4MIND has made substantial outreach progress in the initial phase of its project. By defining and establishing a clear target audience, the

consortium laid a solid foundation for its communication and dissemination efforts. The ability to effectively engage with this audience and achieve communication and dissemination goals within the first part of the project speaks to the effectiveness of the strategies and efforts put in place. This sets a positive trajectory for the project moving forward, indicating strong potential for continued success in engaging with stakeholders and advancing its C&D objectives.

4.2 DataNexus Cluster

EXA4MIND has taken a significant leadership role in bringing together seven sister projects from the HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05 - Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions (RIA) call under the **DataNexus Cluster**. Each project brings unique expertise and perspectives to the group, and by forming this cluster, we can collaborate more effectively, share resources, and potentially achieve greater impact in the field of extreme data mining, aggregation, and analytics technologies through supporting C&D efforts, research, innovation and collaboration. The seven projects participating in this cluster are: **EXTRACT, EFRA, GraphMassivizer, NEARDATA, SYCLOPS, EMERALDS and EXA4MIND**.

The aims and objectives of the cluster are:

Communication and Dissemination: ensure broader visibility, awareness, and engagement regarding all projects' objectives.

- ◆ Establish a C&D strategy that includes sharing and promoting each other's activity (if/when relevant), and a joint presence on social media channels, for example through joint campaigns and features in each other's newsletters and news section etc.
- ◆ Collaborate with other media and initiatives to amplify projects' messages, increase awareness, and reach wider audiences.
- ◆ Meet monthly (in the first 6 months) and two monthly after - to create momentum and investigate potential avenues for collaborative C&D.

Joint events and activity: facilitate exchange and foster knowledge sharing

- ◆ Organise workshops, webinars, and seminars to facilitate dialogue and exchange of ideas among project members and further interested parties.
- ◆ Plan and execute events such as conferences, symposiums and roundtable discussions to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among project partners.
- ◆ Identify key themes and topics relevant to the project objectives and invite experts and stakeholders to contribute insights and perspectives.

Joint research: support and facilitate opportunities for joint investigation

- ◆ Facilitate collaboration among project partners to identify research priorities and opportunities for joint investigation.

- ◆ Encourage the sharing of resources, methodologies, and best practices to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of joint research efforts.
- ◆ Monitor and evaluate the impact of joint research initiatives.

The cluster already established its **name** and **branding** (see Figure 41 and Figure 42) and has published its first joint **press release**. The cluster has been featured at the Adra-e European Convergence Summit 2024⁴⁸ and joined the HRBooster for Service 1 (Module B)⁴⁹. The next activities planned for the cluster are the attendance to EBDVF 2024⁵⁰ and a potential workshop at HiPEAC 2025⁵¹.

Among the next tasks for the cluster, we plan to:

- ◆ Feature the cluster on all project websites.
- ◆ Feature the cluster on the AI on demand EU platform.
- ◆ Continue to work with the HRBooster as a cluster.
- ◆ Support each other's C&D activity.
- ◆ Share C&D resources (eg. Newsletters, events, etc.)
- ◆ Attend events together: already discussing attendance to EBDVF 2024 and HiPEAC 2025.
- ◆ Organise webinars, workshops and/or any other training activity together.

These tasks collectively demonstrate a commitment to collaboration, mutual support, and maximizing the impact of the DataNexus Cluster's efforts in advancing the field of extreme data mining, aggregation, and analytics.

⁴⁸ Adra-e European Convergence Summit 2024 - <https://adra-e.eu/events/european-convergence-summit-2024> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

⁴⁹ HRB Module 1 (Service B) - <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/HRBApplications/ApplicationForm>

⁵⁰ EBDVF 2024 - <https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

⁵¹ HiPEAC2025 - <https://www.hipeac.net/2025/barcelona/#/> (Accessed on 14/06/2024)

Figure 41: Examples of Data Nexus Cluster Branding

Figure 42: First Data Nexus Poster/Visual

To reach a wide audience and keep stakeholders informed about the activities of the DataNexus Cluster, group related activity will be communicated and disseminated on the projects' social media and dissemination platforms (ie. project website). By leveraging social media and the project websites effectively, the DataNexus Cluster will effectively communicate its activities, engage with stakeholders, and maximize the impact of its efforts.

5 C&D Related Internal Governance and Monitoring

Internal governance and continuous monitoring of the C&D plans are fundamental to EXA4MIND's outreach success. They empower the consortium to anticipate and mitigate any deviations affecting the project's timeline or its resource allocation. It also addresses potential implementation issues and helps assess whether further action is required to ensure targets are met.

5.1 C&D Internal Governance

A solid internal governance plan is key to ensure that interests are aligned within the consortium, and that everybody is duly informed of the latest C&D developments.

In the last 18 months the consortium has been proactive in ensuring effective communication, maintaining quality standards, and fostering collaboration among consortium partners:

- ◆ **WP7-specific internal follow-up meetings:** Regular meetings focused on specific workpackages are crucial for maintaining alignment and tracking progress, especially in complex projects.
- ◆ **Two weekly short meetings** have been established with the project coordinator and scientific coordinator. These frequent check-ins with key coordinators are essential for ensuring that any issues or concerns are addressed promptly.
- ◆ **VPI representatives** contribute to the execution of communication and dissemination activities. VPIs involvement ensures that the project's messaging reaches its intended audience effectively.
- ◆ **Quality assurance** measures helped EXA4MIND deliver consistent, reliable, and satisfactory outcomes while minimizing risks.
- ◆ The **15-day review period** for all published material ensured thoroughness and collaboration among consortium partners. This practice likely helps maintain consistency and accuracy in published materials.

5.2 Continuous Monitoring

Internal communication and dissemination reporting tools and resources are available to all partners in the project repository. Providing internal C&D reporting tools and resources to all project partners helps foster transparency and accountability. By enabling partners to track their individual efforts, these tools empower them to actively contribute to the project's overall communication and dissemination goals.

The activity tracker lists and reports efforts linked to communication and dissemination of the project and its results. This tracker includes information about events, publications, presentations, articles, social media and more.

In this activity tracker we also host an internal database with a compilation of shared resources available from each partner for outreach purposes. This database is periodically updated to pool new resources and serve as a common knowledge base for all outreach efforts.

Lastly, EXA4MIND C&D plan establishes monthly communication cycles that include a set of specific actions (e.g., ad hoc campaigns in social media, scheduling of posts and news, identify opportunities, etc.). Actions in each month are reviewed internally on a weekly basis and are presented at project monthly WP7 meetings. This tool also helps keep track of all external mentions, articles or press features for the project.

6 Conclusion

As seen above, the main goal of WP7 is to fast-track and amplify knowledge transfer between EXA4MIND and its target stakeholder base, reinforcing the value streams of the project and capitalising on the results obtained. This report demonstrated the progress and effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken as part of the project in the first 18 months.

This deliverable revised the overall objectives for communication and assessed EXA4MIND C&D tools (visual identity, online channels, and promotional material). We can conclude that branding is established and memorable, the project website is gaining high visibility, and EXA4MIND social media channels are actively engaged, with 7% engagement rate and 78,000 impressions achieved.

EXA4MIND is an avid promoter of Open Science via its social media channels, website, ZENODO, YouTube and GitLab. On these platforms we feature publications, research, newsletters, events, achievements, application cases progress, and stakeholder engagement activity. Additionally, this effort is reinforced by the members' individual efforts to feature the project and share research via their own social media channels and online platforms. Members contributed with 17,000+ impressions supporting the project's reach.

The project achieved over 3,000 contact points via press releases, campaigns, mentions, publications, and events. The promotional branded material was featured in both hard copy and digital format, at over 20 events, 5 booths and meetings.

In terms of stakeholders' engagement, members engaged with more than 22 single initiatives around HPC, Extreme Data mining and analytics, and more specifically within data science & Big Data, computer science, Open Science &

Research, HPC, Agriculture (data related), 6G, AI and automotive, such as EUDAT, BDVA and EuroHPC. Moreover, in April 2023 EXA4MIND successfully led the formation of the DataNexus cluster with sister projects from the HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05 - Extreme data mining, aggregation and analytics technologies and solutions (RIA) call.

In this deliverable we also reflect upon the project dissemination plan, that intends to raise awareness of project results, promoting understanding and encouraging action among key target audiences. The execution of this plan facilitates the uptake of outcomes and best practices, and also promotes research insights and breakthroughs, thus reinforcing the impacts described in the DoA.

Through its dissemination efforts EXA4MIND achieved 13 scientific publications (published/accepted/under review), 35 awareness publications and 550+ downloads in ZENODO.

Regarding outreach and networking members attended over 20 events and 3 training activities. EXA4MIND plans to develop its training program during the second part of the project and the second summer school is already in the pipeline.

Lastly, Section 6 reflects upon C&D internal governance and continuous monitoring, as key to ensure that interests are aligned within the consortium, and that everybody is duly informed of the latest developments.

The monitoring data demonstrates that our communication and dissemination efforts are successful and that we are reaching the right audiences. This is demonstrated by the engagement rates, by the sectors that are engaging with the published materials (social media platform analytics) and, for example, with our experts being selected to be part of relevant expert groups and working groups, like for example StandICT Data experts' group and the EOSC_CZ Data Management for Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning working group.

In summary, the initial phase of the project has been successful in identifying and engaging the target audience. Now that we have established a solid foundation, it's important to continue building on this success to continue to effectively engage with our target audience, achieving the long-term communication and dissemination goals.

For the second part of the project, EXA4MIND plans to continue to build its community via its public presence by putting into practice strategic engagement, consistent communication, and creating value for its members. By following these steps, EXA4MIND will build a strong public presence that not only attracts new members but also fosters a loyal, engaged, and thriving community.

The C&D activities, designed to maximize the visibility and impact of EXA4MIND project within the target audience, already planned for the second part of the project are:

- ◆ Produce a video to further disseminate the project.
- ◆ Establish the project database and run mail campaigns.
- ◆ Continue to lead the DataNexus Cluster and to organise one joint session.
- ◆ Expand our community via training and teaching.
- ◆ Continue to promote Open Science.
- ◆ Produce and promote a position/insight paper.
- ◆ Continue to produce more scientific journal and conference publications.
- ◆ Attend 15+ events.
- ◆ Organise 12 webinars and workshops.

Implementing these strategies will contribute to the effectiveness and sustainability of the communication and dissemination efforts. Building a strong and engaged community is crucial for the long-term success and impact of EXA4MIND. By consistently engaging with the relevant audience through various channels and providing valuable content and opportunities for interaction, EXA4MIND will foster a sense of belonging and loyalty among its community. This, in turn, will lead to greater support, collaboration, and ultimately, the achievement of the project's goals.

7 References

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